

THE APPLICABILITY AND RELIABILITY OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PLASTIC COMPOSITE (T-1000G/EPOXY 3651) TO HELICOPTER BEARINGLESS ROTOR FLEXBEAM

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SUMMARY: The helicopter bearingless rotor flexbeam usually is made of Glass-fiber composite. In the future, carbon-fiber composites can replace the GFRP as flexbeam material due to their superior fatigue strength. This research examines the feasibility of CFRP, especially, unidirectional (T-1000G/Epoxy3651) materials as future flexbeam material. Tension-Tension fatigue tests confirmed the superiority of (T-1000G-Epoxy3651) comparing with GFRP (T-glass/Epoxy3651) in term of axial stiffness, which is desirable against flapping motion. Tension-Torsion fatigue tests simulating the Pitch change and centrifugal forces encountered by the rotor flexbeam showed excellent torsional capability of the T-1000 CFRP material. In order to evaluate the fatigue life and to reach simple optimum design, FEM analysis were carried out for Flapping and torsional sections of the flexbeam which revealed unlimited fatigue life of the CFRP material for both sections, but with CFRP torsional section needed more control loads which considered as the only disadvantage of the CFRP material.

KEYWORDS: bearingless, Flexbeam, CFRP, Tension-Torsion fatigue, Torsional section, FEM.

INTRODUCTION

Helicopter rotor structure is very complex system where complicated loading conditions exist. The loading conditions are more critical and severe at the rotor head, where the actual helicopter rotor head encounters four kinds of loads, the first one is the flapping or out of plane bending moments which is the result of the aerodynamic instability around the rotor system [1]. The second load is the in-plane bending moment or the lead-lag motion resulting from the drag forces. And for a helicopter to fly, the blade is needed to be twisted and that what is called the pitch change control which results in the torsional loads. In addition to these three loads, there is a centrifugal forces resulting in tensile loads acting on the blade and rotor head. In order to accommodate all these motions, a set of bearings are used for each motion on its respective axes. Fig.1 shows a simplified schematic drawing of the rotor head and its loading conditions with bearings image.

A new rotor concept designed to reduce the complexity, weights and maintenance costs through the elimination of all hinges and bearings became feasible through a specialized use of composite materials [2]. The unique anisotropic modulus characteristics of fiber reinforced materials made the bearingless rotor system a reality. Since the structural connection between the rotor hub and the blade is required to have high flexural rigidity coupled with low torsional rigidity and adequate fatigue life, the unidirectional

Fig.1: Simplified Schematic drawing of the rotor head, bearings image and flexbeam.

composites best suit these requirements. This structural connection is called the flexbeam which is the principal element of the bearingless rotor system. The flexbeam should accommodate all the motions through elastic flexing and twisting. The GFRP Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastic Composites have been used for the flexbeam since the interception of the Bearingless rotor system in 1988. But, the advancement of the CFRP fabrication made it available to the aerospace industry at competitive prices and better qualities like improved elastic capabilities combined with good fatigue strength. In this research, the applicability of the new unidirectional CFRP material (T-1000G/Epoxy) to the bearingless rotor flexbeam is examined through the characterization of the Tension-Tension and Torsion-Tension fatigue behavior, designing and analyzing the flexbeam by utilizing ABAQUS FE code. Due to the specific modes of load acting on one region more or less than the other region along the flexbeam, the analysis is done separately by dividing the flexbeam to two section, flapping section and torsion section as shown in Fig.1.

MATERIALS

Unidirectional T-000G/Epoxy3651 (CFRP) material is the main material of this study along with unidirectional T-glass/Epoxy3651 (GFRP) material for comparison. Both material were supplied in Prepreg form by Toray.Inc and were autoclave cured at 180° for 2 hours. The Tension-Tension coupons have 150 mm as gage length with 15 mm width and 1 mm thickness except the T-glass material has 1.5 mm thickness. Whereas Torsion-Tension specimens are 100 mm as gage length, 15 mm width and 5 mm thickness. Fig.2 shows T-T coupons and Torsion-Tension specimens.

Fig.2: Test coupons.

THE PROCESSES

The processes are divided to two sections; the first is the Flapping section fatigue life evaluation and design optimization through FE code and its associate Tension- Tension fatigue testing. The out-of-plane bending moment is the most critical loads acting on this region. While the second is involving the Torsion section fatigue life evaluation and design optimization and its associate Torsion-Tension fatigue testing. The most critical load on this region is the torsional loads.

EXPERIMENTS

To establish the S-N curve, around 8-10 coupons for each material were subjected to Tension-Tension fatigue tests at different constant stress amplitude and at an R-value of 0.1 and frequency of 5 Hz. Torsion-Tension fatigue tests were conducted under constant degree amplitude with 0° as mean degree (±twist degree fatigue tests) and with, simultaneously applied, constant tensile load value of 18.75 kN equivalents to 250 MPa simulating the centrifugal force encountered in the actual helicopter rotor head. The frequency was 1 Hz for tests more than 10 degree and 2 Hz for tests less than 10 degree. All tests were carried out at room temperature and normal humidity. There was also other supplementary testing which was necessary for the input data of the FEM analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The S-N curve is plotted as Maximum cyclic stresses versus the number of cycles to failure in semi-logarithmic scale. CFRP composite exhibited excellent fatigue resistance with only 30 % decrease in strength at 10⁶ cycles, while GFRP strength decreased to about 60 %. The mean S-N curve was drawn by utilizing the following equation

$$\sigma_m = \sigma_{uts} (m(\log N) + b)$$

Where m and b are material constants and N is the number of cycles to failure.

To account for the scatter of S-N data, a reduction factors were applied leading to reduced (working) S-N curve as shown in Fig3 for CFRP composite. Since both materials have the same matrix material but different fibers, therefore, the fibers are to be looked at to reach reasonable interpretation of the fatigue test results. With the long-life cycling (High cycles region), the composite failure is dominated by matrix material, Since glass fiber has low modulus as

compared with carbon fiber, the strain at static failure is large as the monotonic tensile test revealed. Cycles at strain level less than the static failure and greater than the matrix endurance strain, results in matrix fatigue failure followed by composite failure. With carbon fibers, however, a different mechanism operates. Because of their high modulus, the strain level at which static fracture occurs is very small which is well below the endurance strain of the matrix. And that's may explain the fatigue superiority of the CFRP composite.

Fig.3: UD-CFRP S-N curve.

The flapping section optimizations were carried out through FEM analysis of two designs, the inboard tapered design and straight design whereas both designs have the same H cross-section. The H shape cross-section was chosen to avoid the central crack which was reported to occur during the bench fatigue tests by some helicopter manufacturers and these central cracks may occurred due to the large width/span ratio [3]. Out-of-plane bending moment of 3000 N-m and tensile load of 250 MPa simulating the actual extreme maneuver loadings encountered by the helicopter rotor flexbeam were applied. Normal tensile and compressive stresses along fiber direction were the constraints of the flapping section design optimization. The FEM analysis of both designs as shown in Fig.4 and 5 revealed that maximum axial stress is far below the threshold strength of the CFRP working S-N curve. While was just below the GFRP working S-N curve. Proving CFRP (T1000G/Epoxy3651) material can offer reliable unlimited fatigue life when used for the flapping section of the flexbeam. The straight design is preferable over the tapered one, due to the lower cost and ease of fabrication beside the lower weight.

Fig.4: FEM analysis (normal stresses) of the tapered CFRP flapping section.

Fig.5: FEM analysis (normal stresses) of the straight CFRP flapping section.

Static torsion test results showed that CFRP material needed slightly more input torque value to have the same twist rate of GFRP material, and this may attribute to the fact that when laminate is twisted, an axial stress is generated due to the shortening of the length and these axial stresses is proportional to the input torques leading to the proportionality relationship between the axial elastic modulus and input torques [4]. Since CFRP material has larger axial modulus, thus needing more input torques. The static Torsion test also revealed no apparent fracture for all specimens until twist degree of 30°equivalents of twist rate value(twist degree to gage length ratio) of 0.3,except for small permanent deformation for specimens exceeded twist rate of 0.2 or 20°.Therefore, before starting Torsion-Tension tests, a new fracture criterion has to be decided. Since the stiffness and rigidities of the material is very critical aspect of the functionality of the helicopter rotor flexbeam. A 10% reduction in rigidities is set as a new fracture criterion for the Torsion-Tension fatigue tests.

Torsion-Tension fatigue test results revealed that (T-1000G/Epoxy) material has threshold twist rate value of 0.08 at one million cycles as shown in Fig.6 where the twist rate versus number of cycles to failure is plotted. Since helicopter rotor flexbeam has maximum twist rate of 0.05, the T-1000G/Epoxy3651 material is considered to possess an excellent torsional capability to be used as torsion section material.

Fig.6: CFRP twist rate versus cycles.

The same straight design of the flapping section with the same H cross-section, but with double length was used as torsion section design optimization. The same design was chosen, because if proved it is usable as torsion section, one set flexbeam can be fabricated with lower cost. FEM design optimization with shear strains of 1 and 2 plane as the constraints revealed that under twist rate of 0.05 which is the maximum twist rate of the actual helicopter flexbeam, the maximum shear strain of the T-1000G/Epoxy3651 material analysis is well below the corresponding shear strain of the threshold twist rate proving the good torsional capabilities of this material. Fig.7 shows the CFRP FEM analysis results. The same optimization was also carried out for T-glass material and comparing the two results, T-1000G/Epoxy3651 material needed about 15 % more input torques which is considered as disadvantage. As mentioned previously, the larger axial modulus of the CFRP is generating larger axial stresses, thus larger input torques needed.

CONCLUSIONS

Tension-Tension fatigue test results confirmed the superiority of the CFRP (T-1000G/Epoxy3651) materials where the strength decreased only to 70% after one million cycles. While in case of GFRP (T-glass/Epoxy3651), the strength was reduced to about 40% after one million cycles. FEM design analysis and optimization of CFRP (T-1000G/Epoxy3651) showed unlimited fatigue life for both H cross-sectioned tapered and straight flapping section designs.

Static torsion test showed that CFRP needed slightly more input torques and also showed no apparent failure until twist rate value of 0.3, Therefore, a failure criterion was set as 10% reduction in Torsional rigidity.

Torsion-Tension fatigue test results revealed the good torsional capabilities of T-1000G/Epoxy3651 material with threshold twist rate value of 0.08 after one million cycles. But The FEM design analysis and optimization with the H cross-sectioned straight design revealed that CFRP (T-1000G/Epoxy3651) material needed about 15% more input torques when compared with GFRP (T-glass/Epoxy3651) material, thus needing more control loads and power and this is the only disadvantage of the CFRP material. Therefore, CFRP can offer much longer fatigue service life, but with more power needed for control loads.

Fig.7: CFRP torsion section shear strain analysis.

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